

broadcast in field water at 1.5 kg ai/ha 10 d after transplanting Jaya. Soil samples were collected randomly from treated and untreated plots 1 d before treatment (DBT) and 7 and 14 d after treatment (DAT). Culture media for fungi and bacteria were prepared and inoculated using the Ricker and Ricker (1936) procedure. Fungus colonies were counted 3 d after incubation and bacteria colonies 7 d afterward. Two subsamples of each sample were evaluated in the laboratory to determine mean fungi and bacteria population per gram soil.

With time, both fungus and bacteria populations were inhibited by all insecticides except ethoprophos, where

Population^a of fungi and bacteria in rice rhizosphere soil treated with 6 granular insecticides at Bhubaneswar, India, Jun-Dec 1983.

Treatment	Population ($\sqrt{x + 0.5/g}$ soil)					
	Fungi ($\times 10^3$)			Bacteria ($\times 10^6$)		
	1 DBT	7 DAT	14 DAT	1 DBT	7 DAT	14 DAT
Untreated	5.4 bc	5.0 c	4.3 d	1.5 a	1.7 d	1.8 d
BPMC	5.3 bc	1.9 a	1.5 abc	1.7 ab	1.4 bc	1.2 ab
Carbofuran	5.8 d	3.4 b	1.3 abc	1.8 ab	1.6 cd	1.5 c
Carbosulfan	8.7 e	4.8 c	1.9 bc	1.6 ab	1.3 b	1.3 bc
Chlorpyrifos	4.7 b	2.8 b	1.2 ab	1.9 b	1.5 c	1.2 ab
Ethoprophos	5.4 bc	1.6 a	2.0 c	1.6 ab	0.9 a	1.2 ab
Phorate	3.9 a	3.3 b	1.0 a	1.6 ab	1.5 bc	1.1 a

^aSeparation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level.

populations increased 14 DAT (see table). We are studying the long-term

effect of these chemicals on microflora. *J*

Plant parasitic nematodes in rice fields under freshwater and saline soil conditions in Orissa, India

S. Ray and S.N. Das, *Nematology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, 751003, India*

Rice is extensively grown in Orissa, from the saline coastal belt (SCB) to the

interior districts with freshwater habitats (FWH). An examination of 75 rice rhizosphere samples from FWH [where the electrical conductivity of saturation extract (ECSE) ranged from 0.75 to 1.60 mmho/cm and the osmotic pressure (OP) of the soils registered 0.27 to 0.57 atm] revealed associations of 20 plant parasitic nematode species. Twelve samples from the SCB (ECSE, 2.87 to

5.85 mmho/cm and OP, 1.03 to 2.10 atm) yielded 6 plant parasitic nematodes, 5 of which also prevailed in FWH. The frequency and density of nematodes prevailing in the two habitats were varied (see table). Of all the parasites, *Hirschmanniella gracilis* was the most adaptable followed by *Criconebella ornata*. *J*

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with rice under freshwater and saline soil conditions in Orissa, India.

Species	Freshwater habitat ^a		Saline coastal belt ^b	
	Frequency ^c (%)	Density ^d (no.)	Frequency ^c	Density ^d (no.)
<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>	25.9	M - H	-	-
<i>H. crenacauda</i>	10.4	H	-	-
<i>H. pseudorobustus</i>	30.3	M - H	-	-
<i>H. abunaamai</i>	1.5	M - H	-	-
<i>H. ptercercus</i>	5.2	H	-	-
<i>Hoplolaimus indicus</i>	8.8	M	-	-
<i>H. columbus</i>	-	-	25.0	L
<i>Tylenchorhynchus mashoodi</i>	46.6	M - H	25.0	L - M
<i>Pratylenchus zaeae</i>	16.7	M - H	-	-
<i>Hirschmanniella gracilis</i>	61.4	H	100.0	M - H
<i>H. mucronata</i>	25.9	M - H	-	-
<i>Hemicriconebellodes cocophilus</i>	2.2	L - M	-	-
<i>H. mangiferae</i>	0.7	L	-	-
<i>Criconebella ornata</i>	7.4	M - H	33.3	M
<i>Caloosia exilis</i>	18.5	M - H	8.3	L
<i>C. heterocephala</i>	2.2	L - M	-	-
<i>R. reniformis</i>	2.2	L - M	-	-
<i>Heterodera</i> spp.	1.5	L	-	-
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	23.8	L	58.1	L
<i>Siddiqia citri</i>	3	L	-	-
<i>S. boshi</i>	1.5	L	-	-

^aECSE = 0.75-1.6 mmho/cm; OP = 0.27-0.57 atm. ^bECSE = 2.81-5.85 mmho/cm; OP = 1.03-2.10 atm. ^cOut of 75 samples from FWH; out of 12 samples from SCB. ^dL = light = less than 100 in 250 ml of soil sample. M = medium = 101-500 in 250 ml of soil sample. H = heavy = more than 500 in 250 ml of soil sample.

Black beetle — a serious rice pest in western Himalayas

N.K. Shah, *Vivekenanda Laboratory, for Hill Agriculture (ICAR), Almora 263601 (U.P.), India*

Extensive field surveys conducted in the 1981-83 kharif season showed that black or Bhatula beetles *Heteronychus lioderes* Redt infest the low-lying irrigated as well as unirrigated rice fields in western Himalayas. This beetle is a serious menace to both transplanted and direct seeded rice in irrigated and rainfed areas. Fields enriched with humus or supplied with a high quantity of decomposed or undecomposed farm-yard manure (FYM) are more prone to beetle attack. In such fields, 20-40% of damage to rice is done by these notorious soil-inhabiting pests. Seventy of damage depends upon the soil type, FYM applied, and the moisture content of the field.

In the initial stages of infestation, the central leaves of the plant dry up, like those of plants under stem borer attack. The beetle burrows into the base of the rice plant and cuts the stem from the ground level below the soil surface. After feeding on one plant, the beetle feeds on another from the same hill thus

killing the entire hill. A maximum of 5 beetles per hill (av 2) were observed.

The beetles cause patchy damage in the field. Their peak activity period is at night. Peak damage by this pest is observed in Jan-Jul when the crop is in the vegetative growth stage.

This pest attacks rice seedlings in the

nursery stage and also the irrigated crops in flooded fields. Severe infestation by black beetles is sporadic and normally restricted to small areas. Only rice is attacked by this insect pest while other kharif crops remain unmolested under natural infestation conditions. *J*

Effect of *Leptocorisa* sp. on rice grain filling

D. Delpachitra, and D. L. Wickramasinghe, Regional Agricultural Research Centre, Bombuwela, Sri Lanka

Leptocorisa sp. are common rice bugs in the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka. Nymphs and adults damage rice from flowering through dry dough stage.

We recorded damage caused by *Leptocorisa* sp. in observational trials with BW267-3 and Bg 94-1. Agronomic practices were common to all treatments. Complete insect control was used from seeding to flowering.

At early flowering, 12 panicles were randomly selected. Six were placed individually in plastic cages with 10 *Leptocorisa* nymphs/cage, and 6 were caged without insects. Cages were checked daily and insect density was maintained until harvest. Grain discoloration, percent unfilled grains, and grain weight were recorded. Grain weight was determined by weighing the

whole panicle, which included filled, partially filled, and unfilled grains.

Nymphs began feeding at flowering and adults fed until hard dough stage. Although puncture marks were not visible, milk exuded from some grains.

Level of grain discoloration was

similar in all treatments, indicating that the insects were not its cause.

Treatments with *Leptocorisa* had nearly 100% unfilled grains (see figure); insect-free treatments had 20% unfilled grains. Average 100-grain weight was 5.5 g with insects and 10 g without. *J*

Controlling brown planthopper (BPH) with granular insecticides in India

N. C. Patnaik, B. Senapati, and B.C. Jena, Entomology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology (OUAT), Bhubaneswar 751003, India

Summer rice (Jan-May) grown on irrigated coastal areas in Orissa is regularly attacked by BPH. In 1981-83, we evaluated 12 granular insecticides for controlling BPH at OUAT.

Three replications of insecticides were broadcast at 1.5 kg ai/ha at 45 d after transplanting in fields planted to

Field evaluation of 12 granular insecticides for controlling BPH, Bhubaneswar, India.^a

Insecticide	Adults + nymphs/10 has at 20-25 DAT			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	1981	1982	1983	1981	1982	1983
Control	40 cd	49 c	1090 e	1.9 a	3.6 a	1.4 a
Bendiocarb 4G	36 bcd	—	—	2.5 abc	—	—
BPMC 4G	21 a	12 a	80 b	3.3 de	4.3 bc	3.7 bcd
Carbofuran	24 ab	12 a	0 a	3.5 e	4.4 c	4.7 d
Carbosulfan	—	25 ab	102 bc	—	4.4 bc	4.2 cd
Carbaryl + lindane	—	—	935 e	—	—	1.5 a
chlorypyrifos	—	34 bc	763 e	—	4.3 bc	1.3 a
Diazinon	—	—	920 e	—	—	2.4 ab
Disulfoton	32 bcd	22 a	245 cd	2.4 ab	3.6 a	3.3 bcd
Ethoprophos	—	—	398 de	—	—	2.6 abc
Isoprocarb	27 abc	13 a	—	2.7 bcd	3.8 ab	—
Phorate	43 de	10 a	645 e	3.2 cde	4.0 abc	2.2 ab
Quinalphos	62 e	—	—	3.0 bcde	—	—

^aSeparation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level; — = not included in study, DAT = days after treatment.